

STAKEHOLDERS' INVOLVEMENT IN SCHOOL INTERVENTION PROGRAMS AND PUPIL'S PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR ENHANCING ACADEMIC SCHOOL PROGRAMS

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ABSTRACT

One of the performance indicators for school performance rests on the Key Result Area (KRA) that is heavily anchored on the Mean Percentage Scores (MPS). To have better results for these performance indicators, the school collaborates with the community to provide responsive quality education by carefully designing, strict implementation, constant assessment and regular adjustment of school projects. This study sought to better understand the relationship between the level of perception of 100 fifth grade students who were chosen using simple random sampling and their academic performance in the five learning areas. The use of descriptive - correlational research revealed that generally, the learners are performing averagely in the five learning areas. Although they view stakeholders as greatly participative of the school's projects, data revealed that there is no significant relationship as to the perception of the respondents in terms of stakeholders' involvement and learners' achievement. It is then further suggested from the findings that stakeholders should participate more in the monitoring, evaluation, and adjustment of school projects and to shift the focus of the study from the result of pen and paper test to skills development. Instead of looking at the projects as merely school projects, future researchers may also consider using the projects as a teaching strategy.

Keywords: stakeholders' involvement, school interventions, pupils' performance